

THE EXTERNAL ENVIRONMENT RELATIONS OF HEALTH INSTITUTIONS**Selami Yıldırım***Doç. Dr., Azerbaijan State University of Economics, Department of Business***Abstract**

Today, health institutions should accurately analyze environmental threats and opportunities and adapt to sectoral changes to sustain their lives. That is, these institutions should participate in change as a part of change. Environmental factors can have determining effects on healthcare institutions, shaping their future. Because today's healthcare institutions provide their services through a massive institutional size, they are significantly affected by environmental factors. In our study, health institutions are evaluated from a systems perspective in connection with their institutional environmental relations. In this sense, the environmental relations of health institutions are examined by employing Roemer's Conceptual Framework.

Keywords: Health Institutions' External Environment, Health Institutions' System Approach, Conceptual Framework of Roemer

Introduction

Health institutions are affected by the environment in which they are located. Therefore, it is a necessity for health institutions to successfully respond to environmental changes in order to sustain their existence. However, managers must comprehend the environmental factors that affect the organization to respond to environmental changes effectively. Furthermore, health institutions must develop feedback mechanisms to monitor and describe their environment, be sensitive to environmental changes, and make necessary adjustments (Robbins, 1990:205).

The environmental conditions in which health institutions operate are changing at an extraordinary speed and, most importantly, competition intensifies with time. Furthermore, today's health institutions have to compete not only with local or national competitors, but also with international competitors.

On the other hand, health institutions are affected by factors not only in their own service environment but also in the general environment in which they are located. This interaction with broad and changing circumstances in both their immediate and wider environment forces health institutions to develop pertinent and implementable strategies. Examples of these changing considerations include the Social Security Institution (SSI)'s adjustment of Health Implementation Practice (HIP) pricing, excessive volatility in exchange rates, and the use of new treatment methods in any branch by rival health institutions.

In the past, health institutions were operating on a small scale, and in a simple and stable environment. That is, they were affected by very few and slowly changing environmental factors. On the other hand, health institutions today are providing services through massive city hospitals, being affected by many, and very rapidly changing environmental factors.

It is also important to emphasize that today's health institutions operate through massive functional units (city hospitals) and provide service 24 hours, seven days a week, and 365 days a year. Moreover, these health institutions have a budget that is equivalent to or more than the health ministry's budget, their budget share for expenditures on resources such as personnel, medication, and medical equipment are enormous, and they use highly advanced technology.

This complex environment has naturally forced health institutions to use the system approach. It is because today's health institutions provide services in an environment where change is constant, where changes take place very quickly, where time must be managed accurately, and where managers must be able to foresee the future.

Furthermore, managers of contemporary health institutions must be able to analyze the environmental factors, aptly respond to changes, and prepare their institutions for the future.

Purpose of the study

The aim of the study is to examine the external relations of health institutions in a comprehensive manner. We attempt to clarify what the concept of external relations means and what its certain implications are for health institutions. By conducting a broad review of the literature, we explore how different researchers working on health institutions use the concept of external relations in their analyses. Literature review reveals that in most of the studies the external relations have been approached from a systems perspective. From a systems perspective, health institutions are described as systems, receiving inputs such as health personnel, medical supplies, medical technology, medicine, finance, patients, and beds from the environment, processing and returning them as outputs such as the number of treated patients, the number of dead patients, quality, patient satisfaction, staff satisfaction, and productivity to the environment, and evaluating inputs and outputs through a feedback mechanism.

The subject has been analyzed in terms of the conceptual framework of the external environment developed by Milton Roemer. We examine the five main elements that make up the conceptual framework of the external environment of health institutions, namely management, services offered, service organization, resource providers, and finance.

Methodology

In accordance with the purpose of the study, we conduct a comprehensive review of the related literature. The main findings of the literature regarding the external relations concept in general and its distinctive implications for the health institutions are assessed by taking the health institutions as systems.

The relationship between institution and its environment: systems perspective

All health institutions are open-social systems and operate within an environment like other organizations. In the most general sense, the environment can be defined as "all the circumstances and factors outside the official boundaries of a health institution that have the potential to affect all or part of the institution and cannot be controlled by the managers" (Daft, 1989: 45). As shown in Figure 1, health institutions are constantly interacting with their environment in terms of both obtaining inputs and providing outputs.

To produce and provide services, health institutions obtain the required resources (inputs) from the environment. That is, health institutions subject inputs obtained from the environment to transformation processes to produce health services. The transformation process is a series of activities that convert inputs into outputs. The easiest way to understand the transformation process in health institutions is to examine the movements of patients within the institution. When a patient arrives at the hospital, she/he is greeted by the public relations department and directed to the outpatient clinics (day care treatment departments). A large

proportion of patients examined in outpatient clinics also benefit from the laboratory and imaging departments (diagnostic service departments). While some patients continue their treatment in the wards (inpatient treatment departments), others receive services from special service departments such as the intensive care unit and operating room.

In addition to clinical activities, health institutions also directly and indirectly provide services to patients through administrative and support departments such as housekeeping, kitchen-cafeteria, security, patient admission and discharge, and archives. The aim of the transformation process is to create value for patients, that is, to achieve improvement in the health status of the patient (treatment of the illness). That is how inputs are converted into outputs in the transformation process. The most important output in health institutions is the number of treated patients. However, the number of dead patients (crude death rate), the quality of the service provided, productivity, staff and patient satisfaction can also be counted among the outputs. Health institutions supply these outputs to the environment in which they are located.

Figure 1. Health Institution: System Perspective

Because they are open systems, health institutions are extremely sensitive to the external environment. Therefore, managers must be aware of the community's assessment of the health institution and closely monitor environmental changes (such as epidemiological, economic, and technological developments). The mechanism that enables a health institution to learn about its environment is called feedback.

Health institutions are seen as sub-systems of the larger system of the health system. Therefore, it is useful to know the basic elements (components) of the health system and the interactions among them to better understand the external environment of health

institutions. Roemer has developed a conceptual framework for examining the health systems of countries.

Health system: Roemer's conceptual framework

Health systems are one of the most complex social systems. It is often difficult to discern the boundaries of the health system because community and individual health are affected by many different factors. In a narrow sense, the health system includes institutions such as hospitals that directly produce and provide health services, family health centers, dispensaries, home care, nursing care centers, outpatient surgical centers, and imaging centers. In a broad sense, on the other hand, in addition to institutions that directly provide health services, the

health system also includes businesses and organizations that produce medical equipment and drugs, develop medical technology, provide service financing, and determine policies and strategies related to the delivery of services. According to Milton A. Roemer (1991: 79), who studied the national health systems of many countries, there are five main components of a health system:

1. Management (Policy and Strategy Development)
2. Services Provided
3. Service Delivery Organization (Programs)
4. Resource Providers
5. Financing (Economic Support)

Figure 2. The Components, Functions, and Interactions in the National Health System

Management (policy and strategy development)

The management components include organizations and institutions that develop a country's general health policies and strategies. These organizations and institutions are primarily responsible for the planning of the health system, the implementation of health-related legal regulations, and the coordination of services. In Turkey, examples of organizations and institutions that develop health policies and strategies include the Grand National Assembly of Turkey, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Development, and the Counsel of Higher Education.

Services provided

In addition to diagnosis, treatment, and rehabilitation of diseases, health services encompass a range of activities related to the prevention of diseases and improvement of the health statuses of community and individuals. That is, health services are services provided by health institutions and professionals for the purpose of prevention and treating diseases and providing rehabilitation for the improvement of public health.

Preventive health services (primary care) focus on protecting individuals and the community from disease-causing factors. Services that aim to prevent the contact of individuals and the community with disease-causing factors are referred to as environment-oriented preventive health services. Examples of environment-oriented preventive health services include supplying clean water, reducing air pollution, controlling waste, providing healthy food and nutrition, and combating pests. Preventive health services are also provided to individuals. Examples of preventive health services for individuals include vaccination services, maternal and child health services (such as prenatal monitoring), early diagnosis services (such as school

health screenings), family planning services, and health education services. Preventive health services are considered primary health services.

Treatment services are health services provided to restore the health of individuals whose health has deteriorated to their previous level of health. Treatment health services are primarily provided by specialist doctors under the responsibility of other healthcare professionals working as a team. On the other hand, rehabilitation services are services aimed at restoring physical and mental skills lost as a result of a disease or an injury.

Health promotion services are services that enable healthy individuals to improve their health. Health promotion services aim to change individuals' health habits and behaviors and improve their health status. Examples of health promotion services include the promotion and popularization of sport activities and efforts to promote healthy eating habits.

Treatment services are primarily provided in secondary and tertiary health institutions (hospitals). The treatment of diseases that cannot be cured through primary health services is carried out in secondary health institutions. In the case of more complex diseases, treatment is provided in tertiary health institutions. Hospitals in district and city centers that do not provide medical education are secondary health institutions. Health services for complex and more serious cases requiring profound knowledge and expertise and technological resources that cannot be delivered in primary and secondary healthcare institutions are provided in tertiary healthcare institutions. Examples of tertiary healthcare institutions include specialty hospitals and research and

educational hospitals. The mechanism that regulates individuals receiving services from primary care, secondary, and tertiary health institutions is known as the referral chain.

Organization of service delivery (programs)

Health services are primarily provided by public and private sector health. On the other hand, almost all preventive health services in Turkey are provided at community health centers, family health centers, and dispensaries established and managed by the Ministry

of Health. Secondary and tertiary health services are provided by public sector health institutions (under the ownership and management of Ministry of Health, Ministry of National Defense, and state universities), private sector health institutions including private universities, and health institutions owned and operated by non-profit foundations, associations, and minorities. Figure 3 shows the distribution of secondary and tertiary health institutions (hospitals) in Turkey according to the organizations they are affiliated with.

Figure 3. Distribution of Hospitals by Year and Ownership

Source: Ministry of Health, Statistical Yearbook, 2017

Resource Providers

Various medical products (drugs, medical supplies, consumables, medical equipment, and devices, etc.) are required for the provision of health services. The process from the production stage (producers) to

the utilization stage (health institutions, patients) of medical products in the healthcare system is known as the supply chain. Figure 4 depicts construct of a supply chain.

Figure 4. Supply System in the Health System.

Producers/Suppliers: Medical product producers can be divided into three main categories: 1) pharmaceutical and pharmaceutical product producers (such as Abdi Ibrahim and Bilim Ilac), 2) medical-surgical material producers (such as Hipokrat), and 3) medical devices producers (such as Balton). Some producers may be included in two or three of these categories. Medical-surgical material producers produce products such as syringes, surgical knives, blood and sample collection kits, hospital laboratory products, wound care products, and stents placed in veins. Medical devices can be described as high-cost, technologically advanced tools and equipment used in diagnosis and treatment (Ozcan, 2009).

Medical and Surgical Equipment Distributors: Medical and surgical equipment distributors are independent intermediary businesses. These businesses purchase products from manufacturing companies, store them, and sell them to hospitals and other health institutions. On the other hand, the intermediaries in the pharmaceutical sector purchase drugs from manufacturing companies, store them, and sell them to health institutions and pharmacies. These intermediaries are called distributors or warehouses depending on their role in delivering products to the end user.

Group Purchasing Organizations (GPO): Hospitals and other health institutions are members of GPOs. The GPOs offer necessary medical products to health institutions economically. There are many hospitals that are members of a GPO. Thus, hospitals can use collective bargaining power when contracting for products and services such as drugs, medical supplies, laboratory materials, medical equipment, maintenance and repair services, information systems, insurance, and nutrition products and services. There are more than 600 GPOs in the US, and half of them work with

hospitals. It is estimated that approximately two-thirds of the \$50 billion spent on medical-surgical materials by US hospitals is facilitated by the GPOs. Furthermore, approximately 90% of drug purchases are also carried out through contracts with these organizations (Ozcan, 2009).

Businesses and organizations that are involved in all stages of the supply chain (production, distribution, and storage) described above are called resource providers.

Education institutions that provide theoretical education and practical training to develop human capital for the health system also fall within the category of resource providers. Namely, medical vocational high schools and universities providing medical and healthcare education and training are resource providers for health systems. In addition, research and development (R&D) organizations that are dedicated to developing innovative methods and medical technology in medical and healthcare disciplines are also considered as resource providers.

Financing (Economic Support)

In addition to the products and human resources expressed above, financial resources are also needed to provide health services. The financing component includes the institutions that facilitate payments for services provided to the public. The Social Security Institution and private health insurance organizations in Turkey are examples of such financial institutions. Financing institutions make payments to both health institutions that directly provide services and institutions that provide resources used in the production of health services. However, health services are not only financed through public and private health insurance, but also through personal out-of-pocket expenses. For example, the copayments made to pharmacies and the

payments made for medical procedures not covered by the insurance companies for aesthetic purposes are out-of-pocket health expenses.

Conclusion

Health systems are one of the most complex social systems. It is often difficult to depict the boundaries of the health system because community and individual health are affected by many different factors.

Changes occurring in their environments force health institutions to change in various perspectives, from the way health services are provided to management, from the use of technology to the use of different financial tools.

Emerging trends in health institutions, such as new treatment methods, changes in economic tools, new forms of competition with other health institutions, the need for managers with ability to think strategically, and changes in healthcare utilization habits, have forced them to respond to other social systems and even become part of these other systems.

If we look from the perspective of health institutions, we can argue that there is an almost unlimited amount of data in their environments. The important thing is that if the health institutions can collect, define,

categorize, process, and evaluate these data, and develop realistic strategies for sustaining and improving the institutions' operational performance.

Lastly, the ways health institutions interact with their environments are very important for understanding their environment. However, being able to fully understand their environments does not mean health institutions can always be successful. It is because of the fact that health institutions may overlook some changes as their environments are very dynamic. may overlook some changes. Furthermore, sometimes health institutions may not be able to obtain information about the environment in a timely manner. Also, health institutions may be inadequate in responding quickly to potential problems due to the reactions of different actors in the environment.

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